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Version:	1	
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2 Goal and Area of Application

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) describes the collection, short-term storage, pre-processing, isolation and final storage of extracellular vesicles from milk (mEVs) using serial differential centrifugation, EDTA treatment and ultracentrifugation.

This SOP has been prepared in the context of a European project focused on the development of antiviral compounds. The mEV preparation generated with this procedure is intended to be used as a biological vesicular component for subsequent fusion with synthetic liposomes, aiming to develop hybrid EV-liposome delivery systems to improve compound biodistribution and antiviral efficacy. The procedure is intended primarily for bovine milk and may also be applied to buffalo, donkey and goat milk, provided that sample-specific yield and quality are documented. Eligible sample types include raw milk, bulk milk, individual milk, colostrum, refrigerated milk, commercial milk and pasteurized milk. This SOP is intended for research use and downstream applications such as EV-liposome fusion, antiviral compound delivery/formulation studies, RNA-seq, small RNA-seq, proteomics, metabolomics and in vitro functional assays.

3 Definitions and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
EVs	Extracellular vesicles
mEVs	Milk-derived extracellular vesicles
PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid tetrasodium salt dihydrate
RT	Room temperature, approximately 18-22 °C
RCF	Relative centrifugal force, expressed as x g
NTA	Nanoparticle Tracking Analysis
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
WB	Western blotting
TSG101	Tumor Susceptibility Gene 101 protein, EV-associated marker
CD81	Cluster of Differentiation 81, EV-associated tetraspanin marker
QC	Quality control

4 Method

4.1 General

The isolation method is based on serial differential centrifugation. Initial low-speed centrifugations remove cream/fat, cells and large debris. EDTA treatment is used to reduce casein micelle

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aggregation and protein complex carry-over. High-speed centrifugation and final ultracentrifugation enrich the mEV-containing pellet.

Because the isolated mEVs may be used for fusion with synthetic liposomes and subsequent antiviral compound delivery studies, the procedure should minimize cellular contamination, fat carry-over, protein aggregates and repeated freeze-thaw cycles. Harsh mixing, detergent exposure and complete over-drying of pellets should be avoided to preserve vesicle integrity and formulation compatibility. Process milk as soon as possible after collection. If immediate processing is not possible, maintain the sample at 4 °C and complete processing within 24 h. Avoid freezing raw milk before pre-clearing, because cell rupture can release intracellular material and compromise EV purity.

If freezing before complete EV isolation is unavoidable, perform all preliminary centrifugation steps up to and including the 10,000 x g step. Freeze only the clarified supernatant after this step, preferably at -80 °C. After thawing, continue from the 35,000 x g centrifugation step.

4.2 Information for consumables / chemicals / equipment

Product / Equipment	Specification / Supplier	Notes
Milk sample	Bovine, buffalo, donkey or goat milk; raw, bulk, individual, colostrum, refrigerated, commercial or pasteurized	Record species and sample type
PBS	Sterile, particle-free PBS or equivalent, pH 7.4	For pellet resuspension and dilution
EDTA tetrasodium salt dihydrate	0.25 M EDTA, pH 7.4	Add an equal volume to the post-3000 x g supernatant
Sterile tubes / bottles for low-speed centrifugation	Any validated supplier	Compatible with 3000 x g and 10,000 x g
Ultracentrifuge tubes	Beckman Coulter polyallomer tubes or equivalent	Must be compatible with the rotor and target RCF
Benchtop refrigerated centrifuge	Equivalent model acceptable	Must reach 3000 x g at RT and 10,000 x g at 4 °C
High-speed centrifuge / ultracentrifuge	Equivalent model acceptable	Must reach 35,000 x g and 200,000 x g at 4 °C
Rotor	SW41 Ti, Type 45 Ti or equivalent	Use only rotors and tubes validated for the required RCF
Laminar flow cabinet	Class II cabinet or equivalent	Required for sterile resuspension/filtration for in vitro use
0.22 um sterile filter	Low protein-binding filter recommended	Use for EV suspension intended for in vitro experiments
Pipettes and sterile tips	Any validated supplier	Use sterile tips for final handling
NTA instrument	NanoSight NS300 or equivalent	For particle concentration and size distribution

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TEM equipment and grids	Validated facility/equipment	For morphology and debris assessment
Western blot reagents	Antibodies against TSG101 and CD81	Species reactivity must be verified
Personal protective equipment	Lab coat and gloves	Minimum PPE for routine non-contaminated milk handling
Low protein-binding sterile tubes	Validated supplier; nuclease-free if RNA analysis is planned	Recommended for final mEV handling and formulation-compatible aliquots
Synthetic liposomes	Prepared according to a separate approved protocol	Downstream component only; preparation/fusion is outside the scope of this SOP

4.3 Responsibilities

Only personnel trained in sample handling, refrigerated centrifugation and ultracentrifugation may perform this SOP. The operator is responsible for sample identification, rotor/tube compatibility, balancing, correct RCF settings, temperature control, and documentation of any deviation from the stated conditions.

Quality control testing may be performed by the operator or by specialized facility personnel, depending on local laboratory organization.

4.4 Safety and waste handling

- Wear a lab coat and gloves throughout sample handling. Replace gloves if contaminated with milk or EDTA solution.
- Handle all milk samples as biological material of animal origin. Non-contaminated milk is considered a food matrix and does not require special disposal beyond local laboratory rules.
- Reject samples suspected of contamination or mastitis. If such samples have already been opened, discard them according to local biological waste procedures.
- Inspect centrifuge tubes before use and respect manufacturer limits for tubes, adapters and rotors. Balance tubes accurately before centrifugation and ultracentrifugation.
- EDTA-containing liquids may be disposed of according to local chemical/aqueous waste procedures for non-hazardous EDTA-containing solutions, unless local rules specify otherwise.

4.5 Procedure

4.5.1 Sample collection, transport and acceptance

Collect milk into clean or sterile containers suitable for the intended downstream use. Label each sample with species, animal or bulk identification, sample type, date/time of collection, volume, storage conditions and operator.

Transport samples at 4 °C. Process immediately when possible and always within 24 h from collection or receipt, unless pre-clearing and freezing are performed as described in Section 4.1.

Reject samples if any of the following apply:

- visible contamination, abnormal odor or abnormal color;
- clinical or laboratory suspicion of mastitis, unless specifically approved for a dedicated study;
- coagulated milk or excessive clotting preventing homogeneous processing;

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- insufficient volume for the planned isolation;
- temperature excursion or transport time exceeding the accepted limit;
- missing or ambiguous sample identification.

4.5.2 Recommended starting volume

No limits for starting volumes if tube capacity and rotor limits are respected. When changing the starting volume, keep centrifugation RCF, temperature and time unchanged, and record the final resuspension volume to enable particle concentration comparison across samples.

4.5.3 Removal of fat, cells and large debris

1. Bring the milk sample to the processing area and mix gently by inversion. Do not vortex.
2. Centrifuge the milk at 3000 x g for 10 min at RT.
3. After centrifugation, remove and discard the upper cream/fat layer. Avoid disturbing the pellet.
4. Recover the intermediate liquid phase into a clean centrifuge tube or bottle.
5. Repeat centrifugation of the recovered phase at 3000 x g for 10 min at RT.
6. Again remove any upper fat layer and recover the intermediate phase, avoiding the pellet.

4.5.4 EDTA treatment and clarification

1. Add an equal volume of 0.25 M EDTA, pH 7.4, to the supernatant recovered after the second 3000 x g centrifugation.
2. Mix gently by inversion until the solution is homogeneous. Do not vortex.
3. Incubate the EDTA-treated sample on ice for 15 min.
4. Centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 1 h at 4 °C.
5. Recover the supernatant without disturbing the pellet. This clarified supernatant may be frozen at -80 °C only if isolation must be interrupted at this point. Otherwise proceed immediately.

4.5.5 High-speed centrifugation

1. Transfer the clarified supernatant into tubes compatible with the high-speed centrifuge or ultracentrifuge rotor.
2. Balance tubes accurately according to the instrument requirements.
3. Centrifuge at 35,000 x g for 1 h at 4 °C.
4. Carefully recover the supernatant. Avoid disturbing any pellet and avoid aspirating material from the tube wall or bottom.

4.5.6 mEV pelleting by ultracentrifugation

1. Transfer the post-35,000 x g supernatant into ultracentrifuge tubes compatible with the selected rotor.
2. Fill, cap and balance tubes according to manufacturer instructions. Use adapters only when validated for the rotor and RCF.
3. Centrifuge at 200,000 x g for 90 min at 4 °C.
4. At the end of the run, remove tubes carefully. The mEV pellet may be small, translucent or not visible.

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5. Discard the supernatant without disturbing the pellet. Leave the tube inverted briefly on absorbent paper if needed, but avoid drying the pellet completely.

6. Proceed immediately to resuspension or storage as described below.

4.5.7 Final resuspension, optional filtration and storage

For most downstream applications, including EV-liposome fusion and antiviral formulation development, resuspend the pellet in sterile filtered (0.22 µm) PBS, pH 7.4. Select the volume according to the expected yield and downstream assay requirements; record the exact resuspension volume. Gently pipette along the pellet area and avoid vigorous vortexing.

For material intended for EV-liposome fusion followed by in vitro antiviral assays, perform final resuspension and aliquoting under a laminar flow cabinet and filter the EV suspension through a sterile 0.22 µm filter. Record that filtration was performed, because particle recovery may decrease.

Final mEV material may be stored either as a PBS suspension or as a pellet. Store at 4 °C for short-term use within 24-48 h. For longer storage, aliquot and store at -80 °C. Avoid repeated freeze-thaw cycles.

4.6 Quality control and acceptance criteria

Quality control should be performed according to the intended use of the preparation. For comparative studies, apply the same QC workflow to all samples in the same experiment.

QC item	Acceptance criterion	Action if outside criterion
NTA concentration	$\geq 1.0 \times 10^7$ particles/mL after final resuspension	Repeat NTA after appropriate dilution; review isolation volume and pellet resuspension if below threshold
NTA size distribution	Expected particle size range: 30-300 nm; main EV-enriched fraction typically 30-150 nm	Document broader distributions; consider repeating isolation or adding additional purification if large particles/debris dominate
TEM morphology	Intact vesicle-like particles with minimal cell debris/background	If debris is abundant, review sample acceptance, pre-clearing and pellet handling
Western blot markers	TSG101 positive and CD81 positive when antibody reactivity is validated for the species/sample matrix	Species- or antibody-dependent marker variation must be documented and justified
Sample traceability	Species, sample type, volume, storage, centrifugation settings and final volume recorded	Preparation should not be used for comparative studies if essential metadata are missing
Sterility for in vitro use	Final handling under laminar flow and 0.22 µm filtration documented	If not performed, label material as not prepared for sterile in vitro use
Compatibility with EV-liposome formulation	PBS pH 7.4 suspension or intact pellet, minimal freeze-thaw cycles, no visible fat layer or coarse debris, QC data available before fusion	Do not use for formulation studies until missing QC or storage information is resolved
Intended use documentation	Downstream use recorded, including EV-liposome fusion, antiviral compound delivery or analytical characterization	Add intended-use information to the processing record before sample release

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Recommended reporting data include starting volume, final resuspension volume, particle concentration, mean/mode particle size, D10/D90 if available, TEM result, WB marker result, storage condition and number of freeze-thaw cycles.

4.7 Troubleshooting

Observation	Possible cause	Recommended action
Low particle concentration	Low starting volume, poor pellet resuspension, particle loss during filtration, sample variability	Increase starting volume, reduce final resuspension volume, improve gentle pellet resuspension, document filtration losses
Broad NTA distribution or many large particles	Incomplete removal of fat/debris, disturbed pellets, coagulated sample	Review sample acceptance, avoid disturbing pellets, consider repeating pre-clearing if sample is still available
Visible contamination or abnormal milk	Contaminated collection, mastitis, prolonged transport	Reject sample or process only under a specific approved study plan
Pellet not visible	Normal for low-yield samples or small starting volumes	Proceed with careful resuspension over the expected pellet area and verify by NTA
Weak or absent CD81 band	Antibody/species reactivity, low EV amount, transfer or WB conditions	Verify antibody suitability and loading amount; document species-specific marker behavior
Poor suitability for EV-liposome fusion	Low particle concentration, excessive debris/fat, repeated freeze-thaw cycles, complete pellet drying or non-sterile handling	Use fresh or properly stored material, confirm NTA/TEM/WB results, minimize freeze-thaw cycles and repeat isolation if formulation compatibility is compromised

5 Further applicable documents

Mecocci S., Pietrucci D., Milanese M., Pascucci L., Filippi S., Rosato V., Chillemi G., Capomaccio S., Cappelli K. Transcriptomic Characterization of Cow, Donkey and Goat Milk Extracellular Vesicles Reveals Their Anti-inflammatory and Immunomodulatory Potential. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2021;22:12759.

6 Annex

6.1 Quick reference workflow

Step	Operation	Condition / note
1	Milk collection / receipt	Keep at 4 °C; process within 24 h
2	First centrifugation	3000 x g, 10 min, RT
3	Second centrifugation	3000 x g, 10 min, RT
4	EDTA treatment	Add equal volume 0.25 M EDTA pH 7.4; 15 min on ice
5	Clarification	10,000 x g, 1 h, 4 °C
6	High-speed centrifugation	35,000 x g, 1 h, 4 °C

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7	Ultracentrifugation	200,000 x g, 90 min, 4 °C
8	Final handling	Resuspend in PBS; filter 0.22 um under laminar flow for in vitro use
9	Storage	4 °C for 24-48 h or -80 °C for longer storage
10	Release for downstream use	Use only if acceptance criteria and intended-use records support EV-liposome fusion or other planned analyses

6.2 Optional processing record fields

Field	Value / notes
Sample ID	
Species	
Sample type	
Collection date/time	
Receipt date/time	
Starting volume	
Storage before processing	
Centrifuge/rotor used	
Final resuspension volume	
Filtration performed	Yes / No
NTA concentration	
NTA size range/mode	
TEM performed	Yes / No
WB markers	
Final storage condition	
Operator/deviation notes	
Intended downstream use	
Freeze-thaw cycles before use	